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Caught Up Between War, Localism and EU Land Policy: Unravelling Local Land Use Decision-Making in Ukraine

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Abstract

In global discussions on land use amid increasing land scarcity, municipal-level decision-making remains underexplored despite municipalities playing a crucial role in regulating land competition. This gap is particularly notable in supranational policies aimed at reducing land consumption which do not account for the diversity of conditions at the municipal level. This article addresses land use decision-making in Ukraine, where pre-existing pressures on land are intensified by the impacts of war and rising demands for land conservation and reduction of land take. Using a new analytical framework, we investigate the relationship between land use pressures, local authorities' perspectives, and policy responses at the municipal level. Focusing on the case of Vinnytsia municipality, we examine current land use measures, supplemented by a Q-methodology study to capture municipal perceptions of prospective land use and the role of municipalities in governing the land. By combining these methods, we explore how three distinct perspectives held by municipal stakeholders inform local policy actions and assess their responsiveness to both current and emerging pressures. The findings highlight that municipalities are often unaware of their long-term role in achieving sustainable land use and further suffer from localism and ineffective multi-level governance arrangements. This points to the need for a more grounded and context-sensitive approach in supranational land use goals and regulations.

Keywords

Land scarcity, land use governance, No net land take, Ukraine, Q-methodology

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Introduction: Local Land Use Governance Research

There is a growing understanding that land use change is one of the key components and causes of global environmental change (Li et al., 2022; Verburg et al., 2015). The competition for land is intensifying and is driven by many socio-economic and technological factors (Smith et al., 2010), such as population growth, economic development and wealth accumulation, as well as the energy transition. Evidence of the unsustainable scale of land conversion to urban use in Europe has been well documented (ESPON 2020), and similar trajectories can be observed in other regions worldwide (van Vliet, 2019).

Land use planning is considered key in controlling land use change and contributing to more sustainable spatial development (Colsaet et al., 2018; Evers et al., 2024; Gerber et al., 2018). Berisha et al. (2023) conclude that national-level planning systems in Europe are behind the major differences in land conversion. Most public/state-led systems are associated with low land conversion even under higher population growth. Similarly, based on the analysis of functional urban areas across the OECD, Schmidt et al. (2021, p. 1194) argued that a 'more institutionalised and coordinated land use planning system will produce more compact development'. Not disagreeing with such claims, we stress that the competition for land at national and subnational scales is highly varied and requires more nuanced analytical approaches (Krawchenko & Tomaney, 2023; OECD, 2017). For the latter, the role of local authorities is crucial due to their direct domain over land use and decision-making powers (Gradinaru et al., 2023).

Although topics of local land management have been tackled by many researchers (see e.g. Debrunner and Hartmann, 2020; Dembski et al., 2025; Dyca et al., 2024; Hartmann et al., 2023; Hartmann et al., 2021; Krigsholm, 2025; Krigsholm et al., 2022; Lönnroth et al., 2024, Shahab et al., 2020), most of the research has a specific sectoral view, focusing on housing development, climate adaptation, or fiscal incentives. As a result, the complex interrelations between the broader range of various land use pressures, actors' perspectives and policy measures have not been substantially conceptualised and researched to date.

Supporting such observation, Evers et al. (2024, p. 123) have recently stated that

“The step between urbanisation drivers and their outcomes consists of development practices. This is the crucial point at which decisions are made about whether, where, and how to convert land to urban use. It is described as a **'black box'** because it cannot be studied at the macro-level: these decisions are taken in a very localised context according to specific (in)formal rules of the game and interactions by a particular constellation of stakeholders.”

Currently, a lack of such theorisation of decision-making on land use on the local level poses both scientific and practical challenges (Gerber et al., 2018; Hengstermann & Hartmann, 2018).

A simple case-by-case approach to the 'local context' appears insufficient for the task of comparing and evaluating policies and measures across various governmental and institutional arrangements and thus severely limits the opportunities for knowledge exchange (Hengstermann et al., 2023).

At the same time, the implementation of three interconnected reforms in Ukraine in 2014-2021 has set the stage for one of the largest transfers of land ownership and land use controls on the European continent in recent decades. Currently, however, there is limited practical and policy awareness of the role municipalities play regarding future land use. We aim to address this issue by analysing municipal land policies in Ukraine against the competing land uses and pressures, exacerbated by war-related disasters and disturbances, while also considering supranational policy goals, such as 'No Net Land Take' (NNLT) by 2050. This last point is supported by the argument that NNLT is having a major transformational effect on local land use planning across the EU (Idt et al., 2025) and, consequently, will strongly impact Ukraine when the EU accession process is complete.

In response to the outlined knowledge gaps and research goals, two main research questions are considered in this article:

- 1) How do local pressures and conditions for land governance in Ukraine relate to the normative expectations set by the state and supranational bodies (the EU)?
- 2) What are the main points of alignment and divergence in opinions on land use among the local authorities and how do those translate into observable policy measures?

The article is divided into six sections. We start by introducing the analytical framework of local land use decision-making, which is used to structure the empirical part of the paper. We then briefly describe the specific pressures for land use in Ukraine and local institutional and governance conditions. Next, we explain the methodology and investigate employed policies in land use on a case study of Vinnytsia municipality. We then generalise the findings based on the Q-methodology survey conducted in 16 urban municipalities with conditions similar to Vinnytsia. Finally, we discuss the results of the analysis and their impacts on the practical and theoretical understanding of local land use decision-making. In the conclusion, we provide a summary of the major implications of the research towards a grounded (supra)national shaping of land use policy.

Local Land Use Decision-Making: An Analytical Framework

Among the multitude of approaches to land governance and land policy (Davy, 2012, 2023; Needham et al., 2019; Vejchodská et al., 2022), we use the combination of new institutionalist approaches as a basis for the analytical framework, focusing on the decision-making processes.

As discussed by Anisimov et al. (2024), singular theoretical institutionalist frames often suffer from distortions in the analysis by over-emphasising actors and their agency, institutional rules, rationality, or the power of discourse, ignoring other dimensions of institutions (see also Peters, 2019). To overcome these biases, we employ several streams of institutionalist theory attuned to the research questions.

Building on the work of Krawchenko and Tomaney (2023), we treat the governance of land use as rules, interventions, and institutions mediated by the authority to achieve desirable land use under relative pressures. In line with a sociological institutionalist view (Peters, 2019), we look at the organisational structure of a municipality as an evolving institution that produces regulation and is influenced by the external ‘governance’ context. In its role as a key mediator and citizens’ representative, a local municipal authority has major legal controlling and decision-making functions regarding land use.

Such authority, though, is far from a monolith with a singular view towards the issue. It incorporates various stakeholders with diverging perspectives towards land use. The discursive institutionalist stream adds another crucial dimension to the analytical framework – one that ideas and imaginaries influence the institutional design, and actors are continuously working out and interpreting them (Schmidt, 2010). Thus, to study local governance of land use, we need to research the perspectives of key stakeholders on regulation and the desirable future condition of the territory.

In turn, the identified perspectives can be traced and linked to observable policy measures. Measures can be categorised as tools (Stead, 2021) or policies (Hengstermann et al., 2023) and, in this study, broadly encompass all types of organisational, communicative, and fiscal instruments or even direct interventions in the land market stemming from the public authority. Employment of measures develops a two-way connection over time, establishing strong problem-solution links in the everyday institutional practice of stakeholders. Thus, bureaucracy learns to deal with problems in a certain way, developing path dependency.

A similar connection is observed regarding the pressures. It has been argued that competition for land is not a standalone driver of specific processes but an emergent property of other drivers and pressures (Smith et al., 2010). Drivers and pressures are two distinct categories of competition for land. Underlying causes (drivers) are trends of a higher order, often shared across regions, while pressures are processes directly influencing the availability or scarcity of land. Drivers are discussed in detail in sectoral literature (e.g., global energy transition, technological advancement, migration, change in general ecological and social perspectives, increase in wealth; Lambin & Meyfroidt, 2011, and Meyfroidt et al., 2013).

Figure 1 – Analytical framework of interaction between pressures, measures, and perspectives in the land use decision-making (own visualisation)

Land use pressures in our framework are ‘visible’ forces of demand for land. These are treated more broadly from the urbanisation drivers (cf. Evers et al., 2024) and can include land demands such as industrial agriculture, solar energy, or even nature restoration projects. In essence, every major claim for a land use change can be treated as pressure. Pressures influence the perspectives by the perceived urgency and impact, while the existing perspectives localise and interpret their relevance in the ‘big picture’ of things, placing them on a relative scale up to complete dismissal. It can then be argued that pressures, perspectives, and measures concerning local-level land use are always relative and interconnected (Figure 1). We use these conceptual categories to structure the following parts of the article, starting with pressures and governance context.

Land Use Pressures and Governance Conditions in Ukraine

Pressures for Land Use

Urbanisation is not the only direction of land use change in Ukraine. While the change from urban to other land uses is very rare, exceptional circumstances observed in Ukraine necessitate a more inductive view of land use pressures. The war of aggression waged in Ukraine by Russia,

particularly since the start of the full-scale invasion in February 2022, has led to major shifts that triggered 'once-in-a-century' decisions around land use, different from the predictable pressures of urban growth, shared across Europe. Three main shifts can be distinguished: war-induced, continuing trends, and supra-national regulatory pressures.

Firstly, the war has resulted not only in an immense loss of human life and the destruction of natural ecosystems but also in the loss of 10% of arable land that is suitable for agriculture in the medium to long term (Kussul et al., 2025), plus an additional 15% of such lands being occupied (Economichna Pravda, 2024). This led to the need to find new areas for agricultural activities in the Western regions. Secondly, with severe war-inflicted damage to sites of energy generation, the energy system and especially electricity networks hang in a very tight balance, which calls for new decentralised energy production, including solar and wind farms (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2024). Yet another land pressure comes from the expansion of industry and logistical networks, caused by shifts in the economic geography of the country, as highlighted by Clem et al. (2024) and Devlin et al. (2024).

In addition, the continuation of several pre-war trends and pressures is visible: suburbanisation by construction of detached housing, both as primary residences and as secondary homes, has gained significant impetus in the last decade (Mezentsev & Kljucko, 2015; Mezentsev & Povotar-Mezentseva, 2017). Southern Ukraine has also been suffering from the loss of agricultural productivity due to salinisation and wind erosion in the arid southern regions, with the growing green water scarcity (Panasenko & Ryabchenko, 2020; Ranu et al., 2024). Lastly, there is a legal requirement for the expansion of natural reserves and protected areas from 6.6% to 12,5% by 2025 which to date has not been achieved (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 2019).

Meanwhile, the effects of the implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy (Commission, 2020) and its key components – the Soil Strategy and Nature Restoration Law, with the targets of the expansion of protected areas, such as no less than 10% of agricultural lands need to have high-diversity landscapes or increased protection regime for the existing natural areas, have still not been considered. Ukraine will likely be subject to the adoption of No Net Land Take (NNLT) as a target indicator by the EU by 2050 (Commission, 2021), starting with the upcoming EU Soil Monitoring Law in 2025. In the latest edition of the Soil Monitoring Law proposal (Council of the European Union, 2024), it has been proposed to be disaggregated into three components: soil sealing, soil destruction, and soil artificialisation. The NNLT approach introduces a binding compensation approach to ensure that new greenfield development is only possible under full compensation elsewhere, such as rewilding and revitalisation of previously degraded areas and habitats.

Beyond Ukraine, NNLT implementation is already a highly debated topic, with multiple concerns raised about 1) the scale and specifics of the measurement, e.g. national, local, regional, satellite and public datasets, planning legislation (Evers et al., 2024); 2) various intensive land occupying activities such as industrial agriculture not being considered 'land take', while unintrusive solar installations are (Decoville & Feltgen, 2023; Marquard et al., 2020); 3) the differing regulatory and policy contexts of its implication (Mazzoleni, 2022). Moreover, NNLT creates a paradox of causing land scarcity locally because of the limitations created by the restrictive policy, irrespective of the specific conditions and needs of the municipality (Decoville & Feltgen, 2023; Evers, 2024). Rewilding and nature restoration can become similarly competing 'sectors' for land use, ultimately adding to, not resolving, the scarcity conundrum (Meyfroidt et al., 2022). As highlighted in a recent special issue dedicated to NNLT in planning, it 'may ultimately jeopardise other equally legitimate public objectives, from housing to economic development' (Idt et al., 2025, p. 341), making it a highly contested political topic. Similar to the findings of Scheurer and Vranken (2024, p. 36), we see a major challenge in the transposition of such supranational aims into national and sub-national regulation, but even more regarding practical local-level implementation (Dembski et al., 2025).

Governance of Land Use

The land use pressures in Ukraine unfold within a dynamically evolving framework for land use governance. It was formed over the last decade by three interconnected sets of reforms: territorial and fiscal decentralisation, spatial planning and construction (Anisimov et al., 2024), and, importantly, land market reform.

The first comprehensive set of administrative, fiscal, and territorial reorganisations started in 2014 under the title of "Decentralisation" (see OECD, 2018, 2022; Romanova and Umland, 2019; Wright and Slukhai, 2021). The reform mainly affected the basic municipal level of governance, resulting in a large-scale and rapid municipal amalgamation, which was undertaken between 2015 and 2020 in two stages: voluntary in 2015-2019 and compulsory in 2020. As a result, close to 12 000 municipalities, mostly sparsely populated rural, institutionally weak, and overdependent on subsidies from the state budget (Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, 2014), were amalgamated into 1469 new units. New, larger municipalities were considered capable of taking over additional functions, including direct control over the use of land outside the settlements' boundaries. The enlarged jurisdictions of municipalities after amalgamation now include heterogeneous assemblages of urbanised areas, cultivated lands, and open natural space. Total municipal control over land use has expanded from just 4% of the national territory (located within the settlements' boundaries) to over 84%. Since 2018, additional measures have been

introduced to transfer the state-owned lands into municipal ownership (Taratula & Stupen, 2018).

The second set of reforms, largely responding to the issues of territorial governance brought up by decentralisation, is related to spatial planning and urban development. Since 2020, there has been a proliferation of statutory and strategic local-level planning documents, and the Comprehensive Plan was introduced as the main statutory plan concerning the use of land (Anisimov et al., 2024; Steinkemper & Vlasenko, 2024). Among other tasks, a Comprehensive Plan sets functional zoning for the entire municipal territory, which should be automatically translatable into the land use codes of the national cadastre via a correspondence table. However, the adoption of Comprehensive Plans has been incredibly slow, with only four municipalities adopting them as of April 2025. Granted the weak financial and staff capacities at the municipalities, as well as emergency war issues and disjointed connections in the planning framework, there is little chance it will speed up much in the foreseeable future (Anisimov et al., 2024).

In parallel with the introduction of new planning instruments, the procedures that guide the change of functional zoning and the issuing of construction permits were altered within a major turn towards digitalisation. Under the guise of the introduction of the State nified construction register (EDESSB) and National digital urban planning cadastre, significant deregulation was achieved. It is particularly manifested in the “affirmative action” concerning the construction of new residential buildings on plots under 500 m² and the simplified and almost “automatic” change of land use functions outside the settlement boundary (Anisimov et al., forthcoming). In place since 2021, these new regulations increase the risk of unplanned suburban growth, forcing municipalities to react rather than proactively manage the development of new areas created by municipal mergers. This risk is especially high for the municipalities that fail to produce Comprehensive Plans.

The third and final set of reforms included the long-debated completion of land privatisation and is related to the lifting of the moratorium on selling agricultural land plots, mostly privatised from collective farmlands. Introduced in 2001 and active until 2020, the moratorium effectively prevented several millions of land plot holders from fully entering the land market, limiting the available transactions to long-term leases. Additionally, since 2008, the World Bank has funded the digitisation of agricultural lands and the creation of a State land cadastre (Torhonen, 2016), which has been instrumental both in securing and enabling ownership rights and in increasing the internationalisation of the major agriculture holdings (Deininger & Ali, 2023) by providing them with better access to international finance as a result of the digitisation of their assets. As

a result, the mobility and value of land resources have increased dramatically (Deininger et al., 2024), but now under the municipal planning mandate.

To sum up, the implementation of these three groups of reforms has transferred a considerable number of territories, assets, and responsibilities over the use of land to Ukrainian municipalities, in contrast with the earlier established practice. It has led to increased agency of municipalities in formulating land use policy goals. However, this was hindered by the wartime austerity measures, inadequate resources and staff capacities to develop the required plans, as well as general lifting or liberalisation of regulations for new construction and (re-)allocation of land. To demonstrate the local circumstances in which the newly gained mandate of the local government is realised through specific measures and policies affecting land use, we present a case study of Vinnytsia municipality in central Ukraine in the following section.

Land Use Policy Measures: A Case of Vinnytsia Municipality

Case Study Design

While we determine the perspectives of local stakeholders based on an aggregate sample of 16 municipalities via Q-methodology, we utilise a single case study to obtain insights regarding local-level land policy measures and visualise their impacts. Based on the analysis of the territorial and land use governance framework in Ukraine, we decided to focus on the urban municipalities that expanded their administrative boundaries during the territorial decentralisation in 2020. The selected municipalities were all formed around so-called “core cities” (cities of oblast significance), a currently obsolete term for the municipalities that enjoyed a higher degree of local autonomy and fiscal decentralisation before the 2014-2020 reform. Besides its significance for territorial statistics, this presupposes a more robust land use planning unit in their administrative structure since before 2020. In such municipalities, the competition for varied land uses for the development of peri-urban territories is also more pronounced (Ivits et al., 2022).

To define a general set of municipalities, we introduced additional quantitative criteria to define the final list in terms of the overall population (over 100 000), the number of settlements (more than one), and the percentage of territorial surplus after the amalgamation (over 20%). These criteria helped to define municipalities with comparable planning capacity and established tradition of local autonomy. The criteria also aimed to ensure the relevance of the amalgamation-related expansion discourse, identifying cases where its scope was hard to ignore. Finally, we excluded municipalities in immediate proximity to the current military line of contact, which are fully preoccupied with sustaining critical infrastructure and basic services and other dire needs of daily recovery, civic defence, and social care.

Vinnitsia represents a typical case (Gerring & Cojocaru, 2016) within the sample, having a medium-sized area of 256 km² (median = 260 km²) and a little over average population (388k, median = 260k), but the number of amalgamated settlements (9) is slightly below the median (15).

Table 1 - Characteristics of the chosen municipalities

	Municipality	No. of settlements	Total area, km ²	Area of admin. centre, km ²	Total pop. (2021)	Territorial amalgamation, %
Criteria	not frontline, urban	>1	-	-	>100 000	>20%
	Ivano-Frankivsk	19	263.8	28.3	287 533	832.20%
	Brovary	4	125.2	35.8	119 573	249.70%
	Bila Tserkva	17	394.4	32.9	218 981	1098.80%
	Vinnitsia	9	256.6	57.2	388 204	348.60%
	Drohobych	34	426.2	11	121 778	3774.50%
	Zhytomyr	2	91.5	59.6	265 126	53.50%
	Kamianets-Podilskyi	13	175.3	27.1	109 064	546.90%
	Kamianske	3	136.3	62.2	236 672	119.10%
	Kremenchuk	5	165.1	88.7	220 619	86.10%
	Lutsk	36	383.1	40.2	240 292	853.00%
	Lviv	20	311.4	80.3	780 804	287.80%
	Mukachevo	18	266.9	27.9	110 483	856.60%
	Poltava	56	550.3	104.2	309 647	428.10%
	Ternopil	11	166.7	38.9	226 594	328.50%
	Khmelnitskyi	25	493.9	92.5	293 223	433.90%
	Chernivtsi	3	180.4	99.2	270 578	81.90%
	Median	15	260.2	48.7	238 482	388.35%
	Mean	17.2	274.2	55.4	262 448	648.70%

Local planning documents, particularly the newly approved Comprehensive Plan, were used to ‘spatialize’ and verify policy commitments where possible. Available secondary sources were consulted, such as reviews, news articles, and official statements. Combined with academic

sources, this information was used to develop a semi-structured questionnaire for in-depth interviews. Nine in-depth interviews were conducted in Vinnytsia to understand the local conditions of farmland conversion, land use pressures, and corresponding authorities' actions and policies. Additional fieldwork, such as site visits and observations of new developments on the city fringes, was carried out in the spring of 2024.

Institutional and Governance Arrangements in Vinnytsia

Vinnytsia has been a frontrunner in the decentralisation reform since 2016, experimenting with buying land from the neighbouring rural municipalities, which were located within the ring road highway encircling the city (Interviewee 2). As a method for price calculation, Vinnytsia used the then-current 10-year land tax extrapolation on the land plots, which they offered to pay to the municipalities in advance. Building on this experience, in 2018, Vinnytsia promoted the village of Desna's amalgamation with the city, concluding the first period of administrative amalgamation.

In 2020, the second and final round of enlargement occurred. By then, local elites and landowners in the municipalities adjacent to Vinnytsia had already uncovered the benefits of self-government and land rights control around the core city and were reluctant to enter amalgamation with Vinnytsia. Instead, it had to amalgamate with several smaller villages lacking political agency, bundled together with the surrounding agricultural territories. The municipality thus expanded towards relatively unconnected and distant villages in the east, with which it had limited economic and infrastructural ties. Assuming responsibility for welfare provision over this territory, Vinnytsia meanwhile failed to secure control over the areas of more intensive development along the major highways to the west of the city.

“Those territories that have joined lie in the east. It would be more correct for the territorial community to unite with the communities on the west because there is no border between cities and villages. We are talking about Vinnytsky Khutory, and in the west, about the Yakushinets village council. Of course, each community had its centres of gravity, power, and business. That is why the Yakushinets village council, for example, did everything to create a territorial community in order not to amalgamate with Vinnytsia.” (Interviewee 2-M)

Today, Vinnytsia municipality has over 256km² of land under administrative jurisdiction, up from 57km² in 2014. Like many other local governments in Ukraine, Vinnytsia is still analysing the scope of available land for future use. Agricultural lands within the municipal boundary both pose questions related to their continued future use and lend opportunities for fast and 'easy' greenfield expansion. The newly 'acquired' land is mostly flat and unbuilt, although it lacks a connection to the existing utility infrastructure networks, especially to potable water and

wastewater pipes. However, the land itself is mostly privately owned, and the municipality has limited regulating powers over its future (Interviewee 1).

Policy Measures Towards Desirable Land Use

To analyse the key proposals for zoning and re-allocation of land in the Comprehensive plan, a scheme of the current land use was prepared at the scale of municipality based on CORINE-derived categories (Figure 2). Zoning codes and density classifiers from the Comprehensive Plan were manually converted into the same categories to facilitate comparison (see Annex 3 for detailed description of the method).

Figure 2 – Current land use in Vinnytsia municipality, according to satellite data, CORINE-derived categories

The new Comprehensive Plan proposes a drastic densification and expansion of the urban fabric. There is consensus about several components, namely the safeguarding of riverbanks against development, somewhat limiting uncontrolled development of detached houses, developing industrial/logistical nodes, and sticking to formal land use prescriptions. However, the current plan development has spurred discussions regarding the extension of urban development beyond the existing borders of the settlements, especially in rural areas (Figure 5).

Vinnitsia municipality formulated several policies that react to the growing competition for land resources. Overall, we identified four sets of measures: *expansion of industry, development of the agricultural sector, new housing construction, and the 'green agenda'*. Some of these directly engage with the pressures for land use, while others focus on broader topics and are harder to spatialize.

The first set is related to stimulating industrial growth. Several hundred hectares are being developed as prospective industrial parks and industrial zones (Figure 3). The municipality heavily invests in land preparation, both via legal regulation (e.g., zoning changes) and via investment in core network infrastructure, such as electricity, water, drainage, and roads. One of the major projects is Vinnitsia Industrial Park in the eastern part of the city. Devised back in 2016-2017, it consists of four main areas: HEAD winter sports equipment (10 ha), Cluster of Refrigerator manufacturing (12 ha), Agrifood cluster Volia (35.7 ha), and Vinindustry (13 ha), each of which has supporting logistics and consulting services. These are situated on previously agricultural lands, thus amounting to almost 100 hectares of land take, including roads and other infrastructure.

“Besides, the local council allocated almost 100 hectares of territory near the Nemyriv highway to the airport as an industrial zone. The strength of this territory, including its decentralisation, is in the sense that it is not the territory that one [market] player took for himself, but it is [multiple] industrial parks that have just been created, which set prerequisites for business development. There are many players, contrary to the usual hierarchical pyramid structure of one company.” (Interviewee 7-B)

The second set of measures relates to the strengthening of the agricultural sector, chiefly through engaging with small local farmers, fishermen, and farmers' markets. The municipality is actively trying to overcome the fragmentation of agricultural activities by providing horizontal coordination mechanisms (Interviewee 4-M). For instance, the newly created Directorate for Strategic Development and Agricultural Policy is organising local small farmers working without legal registration to obtain a tax registration to sell their goods in the city or wholesale markets. There are also various capacity-building activities organised for small and medium-sized farms, such as courses on agriculture, legal advice, and the establishment of local trademarks. The concern of the municipality is the local food security, affordability, and quality:

“We are doing everything to form a food security belt around the city. Large European cities strive to ensure that the products that are grown around the city in a radius of 20 kilometres are all sold in the city (...). In our country, almost ninety per cent of products are brought into the city from outside (regions). We analysed that, for example, a lot of vegetables come from the Transcarpathia and Chernivtsi regions, also from Turkey, even though in our region, this issue can be resolved without problems.” (Interviewee 4-M)

Figures 3a and 3b – Conversion of arable land into new industrial zones adjacent to the airport and rail logistics proposed in the Comprehensive plan in Vinnytsia.

Thirdly, new residential development of various types is promoted by the municipality. Between 2010 and 2020, Vinnytsia has added approximately 75 000 apartments, according to official statistics (SSSU, 2021). New construction should also respond to the future needs of internally displaced persons (IDPs) currently residing in Vinnytsia and war veterans. Three programs are present in this regard. The first one, presented in the form of a Crisis housing plan, encompasses medium and long-term housing programmes of housing development for IDPs, chiefly through reconstruction and densification projects. The second policy direction is focused on low-rise residential estates for middle-income groups. According to interviews and our monitoring on the ground, the development of summer home-type secondary and primary residences is already underway in the suburbs of the city and even outside of the municipal borders. Some officials also stated that:

“First of all, land plots are being surveyed for their transfer to our veterans after their return from the front. Because we understand that, based on the experience of the 2014-2022 Antiterrorist Operation, such a situation [of the transfer of land to veterans] will take place. It is also provided for by the current law on social guarantees for veterans.” (Interviewee 3-M)

Similar to findings from the Netherlands and Germany (Götze & Hartmann, 2021), expectations of future fiscal revenue from such spatial expansion were identified in Vinnytsia. These seem to lack a profound long-term financial modelling, especially regarding servicing new areas of urbanisation, which is notoriously hard to evaluate in advance. Such a form of low-rise urbanisation, however, is contested by the simultaneously proposed high-rise dense development (see new dark red areas in Figure 4) characteristic of the current housing shortage and real conditions of household finances. Households cannot afford to buy spacious detached housing and often move into one-bedroom apartments or even studios with whole families, hoping to settle soon in their own flats and stop wasting money on rent (Interviewee 1-M). It should also be pointed out that the envisioned expansion is not currently supported by infrastructure and utility networks. Meanwhile, ensuring the reach and quality of the networks is one of the key challenges for the enlarged municipality, even without considering the perspective of development outside the settlement area (Interviewee 1-M).

The last set of measures concerning land use is the local green agenda, as laid out in the strategic documents and land and nature preservation research projects led by local institutions (City Institute, Spatial Development Agency). Vinnytsia City Council proactively adopted the EU Green Deal in its resolution and set strategic goals in several sectors to achieve carbon neutrality (Vinnytsia City Council, 2022). One of the projects under this umbrella is a study of previously neglected small rivers and streams as contributors to biodiversity and underutilised public

Figures 4a and 4b – Densification of low-density urban fabric and conversion of rural fabric proposed in the Comprehensive Plan in Vinnytsia

spaces. Subsequent mapping of small rivers was registered as part of land survey results in the cadastre. This initiative started in the city context before the amalgamation, but has been partially extended to the scale of the whole amalgamated municipality. One consequence of this can be found in the draft of the municipal Comprehensive Plan, where some of the newly traced small rivers obtained protective buffer areas.

“Only 9 or 10 objects were previously recorded with buffer zones in the city. When we began to delve into this topic, we found materials from the oblast [region], in which there were many more of them. (...) And after approving the concept, we managed to influence the design process of the Comprehensive Plan and the General Plan. Thanks to this, we have significantly more rivers and streams in this urban planning documentation” (Interviewee 8-M)

Another study on the structure and condition of soils has highlighted that the current agricultural practices, especially on the slopes, are highly destructive to the soil cover and need to be left fallow. Moreover, it identified that some lands were considered degraded by erosion, and they need to be conserved and removed from active agricultural use (Institute of Land Use, 2022). These insights had very limited bearing on the provisions of the Comprehensive Plan, where few restrictions on such uses are present.

Such diverse rationalities concerning the future land use and the policy measures are resemblant to the structure of municipal administration. While Vinnytsia has partially identified the need to carefully manage land, overlapping claims have hardly been treated as a problem, as they are managed by different departments that respond (in)directly to the sectoral land use pressures. The immediate victims of this departmentalisation are mostly agricultural territories with limited protection against conversion (Figure 4b). However, as ongoing urbanisation threatens the local food security objectives, their respective proponents might end up in a direct conflict.

Despite the lack of protected natural lands in the municipality and broader region, the former has been reluctant to propose the creation of new reserves within the Comprehensive Plan or any substantial natural rewilding/regeneration, contrary to what it claims in the official policy. No net land take policy remains outside of the current decision-making in the municipality, and such dimensions as ecosystem services of land also remain undeveloped in the current context.

In summary, Vinnytsia is navigating a complex set of pressures, including land use for new productive functions, the need for cooperation between manufacturers, and the challenge of balancing suburban growth with careful planning. While the municipality remains committed to meeting EU requirements, the spatial effects of the industrial development and suburbanisation are not sufficiently considered, risking excessive land consumption. At the same time, there is a

P-sample

Inferring from our theoretical standing, where we treat municipality as a key institution in land use governance, we sought a broadly representative set of views shared by the relevant stakeholders in the local authority (Van Exel & De Graaf, 2005). The P-sample of participants consisted of four stakeholder groups, following the usual sectoral division of municipal departments in Ukraine, namely, “ecology and nature protection”, “architecture and planning”, “socio-economic development”, and “land use and agriculture”. Each of these groups has a connection to decision-making on local land use and its respective importance. The secondary screening was required to make sure that all the stakeholders were allocated to the proper stakeholder groups.

Out of 60 identified respondents who were contacted by email, we received 24 replies, out of which only 22 could eventually be analysed due to errors, covering 10 municipalities, with the stakeholder group distribution as follows: 10 for architecture and planning, 5 for land use, 6 for ecology and nature protection, and 5 for socio-economic development.

Q-set

The Q-set (or Q sample) is a list of statements that cover the existing representations of a certain topic (named concourse) and often consists of 40 to 50 statements, with fewer statements also considered valid, depending on the task (Van Exel & De Graaf, 2005). Usually, Q-set statements fall under one of three categories: “representation”, “understanding”, and “action” (Watts & Stenner, 2012). We focused on the statements related to “action” due to the future-oriented research questions. “Action” perceptions thus helped connect the stakeholders’ perspectives with observed policy measures and visions of desired land use.

To compose a Q-set, we initially scanned the literature on representations of land use and arrived at 22 statements. It was subsequently expanded to better cover the issue of land use by incorporating findings of the secondary literature (see Annex). We used the case study of Vinnytsia as an additional resource to formulate the statements by extracting data from the local interviews and also amending the statements to better fit the language utilised by stakeholders. To keep the Q set broadly representative while including contrasting and divergent statements, we settled on a total number of 27 statements. As argued in the literature, disregarding the structure and of what the researchers understand as a balanced set of q-statements, it is the subject who gives meaning to the statements by placing them in a sort (Brown, 1993).

The participants completed the ranking according to the configurations in an online Q-sort, placing statements within a pyramid-style grid board from -4 to +4 with 27 slots, and answered a questionnaire commenting on the statements they agreed with most and least.

Limitations

While the Q-methodology allows the systematisation of diverse viewpoints in shared perspectives, it has limitations. First, it doesn't allow generalisations on a larger scale, so findings can't be directly applied to other municipalities in Ukraine with different attributes, especially those heavily affected by the war. Second, the development of Q-statements is inherently shaped by the researcher's agenda. The fixed Q-statements and forced distribution may also limit participants' ability to express their views fully. To address this, we allowed participants to elaborate on their answers after sorting, helping to refine our interpretation of the factors. We cross-validated responses with in-depth interviews and observations from Vinnytsia to make sure there were no major inconsistencies.

Third, although our sample size was limited ($n = 22$), the inclusion of diverse stakeholders provided a well-rounded view of the land use debate. Since we focused on future-oriented "action" statements, we acknowledge that local views on land use governance are still evolving and will need further assessment. Fourth, treating local authorities as key decision-makers, we only contacted respondents within the municipal administration without investigating the views of other stakeholders, for instance, in the private sector or civil society.

Resulting Factors

Subjecting the 22 Q-sorts to factor rotation (Spearman), we were able to identify three perspectives representing the different viewpoints of the participants: Pragmatic, Protective, and Managed Growth. These three perspectives, referred to as factors in the Q methodology, cumulatively explained 48% of the variance. Three Q-sorts that loaded onto more than one factor were disregarded from the analysis ($p > 0.05$). Rankings were produced for each factor and presented in the Annex.

In our interpretation of individual factors, we isolated the consensual statements, emphasising the most distinguishing opinions. Factors are first seen by researchers as composite Q-sorts configured to represent the common viewpoint of people loaded onto a particular factor. To fully understand the composite Q-sort, we used the answers from the accompanying questionnaire of the respondents who were included in the factor. Next, by careful examination of the distinguishing statements, we arrived at the final naming and interpretation.

Table 2 – Main aspects of identified perspectives (factors). More details (Q-set and ranking by factors) in Annex 1.

	Factor 1 Pragmatic perspective	Factor 2 Protective perspective	Factor 3 Managed growth perspective
Key viewpoints based on distinguishing statements and comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High reliance on the Comprehensive Plan; • Rejection of development on arable land; • Curbing expansion of ploughed areas; • Retaining land in communal ownership as a reserve for the future 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low expectations about the Comprehensive Plan • Densification within the existing urban boundary and curbing suburban development; • Consolidating the land owned by the municipality and avoiding selling more of it. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High reliance on the Comprehensive Plan • Prioritising new logistical centres and new industrial parks • Low attention to urban area extension
Number of significant loadings (respondents)	8	9	3
Eigenvalue	7.27201	1.97303	1.32461

Before reflecting on the individual factors, we discuss consensus statements – the opinions on which are aligned across all obtained factors. Notably, the only point of a strong consensus is the reluctance to share the newly gained land use planning mandate with the regional level of governance (avg. +3). Overall expectations concerning the financial gains or losses to the local budget from the outcomes of amalgamation are moderate and cautious (avg. -1). The stakeholders do not see these territories as a source of significant tax income or as ‘black holes’ in future capital expenditures towards developing local infrastructure. There seems to be no strong position concerning the issues of collecting and publishing data on the current land use and the unregulated expansion of ploughed areas, both often alarmingly highlighted as data lacunas at the national level by ecologists. A weak consensus can be observed concerning organising broad stakeholder dialogue both within and outside the amalgamated municipality.

Factor 1 (Pragmatic perspective) embodies a cautious position towards the local land policy informed by the conviction of reaching a mix of functions as its key desired outcome. They simultaneously reject the advance of development onto productive agricultural land (+3, particularly discouraging the sprawl and curbing further expansion of ploughed areas (-4).

The extensive approach to agriculture is not a priority due to the limited territorial [land] resources and it being outside of the focus of the Sustainable Development Goals. (Respondent 6UN7C)

While strongly prioritising the organising role of a future Comprehensive Plan (+4), they discard the possibility of challenging the status quo in terms of plot ownership structure and property restrictions (-3). Perhaps most characteristically, they call for retaining a fair share of communally owned lands in reserve (+3), which we interpret as their acknowledgement of the still emerging and largely incomplete representation of these lands and the actual effect of allocating them to one or other use.

Curbing the development reduces the [infrastructure] maintenance costs on the amalgamated territories. Reserving the [communal] land allows us to sustain it as a resource for the future. (Respondent 87RA7BQ)

The analysis of distinguishing statements associated with **Factor 2 (Protective perspective)** showcases a different modus operandi: future land use goals, such as the expansion of green areas and enforcing their protection, should be achieved more proactively by consolidating the land that is currently owned by the municipality (+3) and avoiding selling more of it (-4).

[Selling the communal land] is a typical short-sighted measure at a local level when the abundance of a certain resource leads to negligence and utilising it as the most basic commodity. Instead, a policy for the transformation of such lands is to be developed, which views them as a sustainable and long-term resource that does not need to result in immediate economic gain but serves as a planning instrument. (Respondent DPMB58KP)

Allocation of plots for development in suburban areas is particularly discouraged (-3), with a priority given to densification within the existing urban boundary through brownfield conversion (+4). Importantly, a Comprehensive Plan is not seen as a chief enabler of consolidating these ambitious policy goals (0), contrary to other perspectives. It can relate to the usually pro-growth aims of such spatial plans, a view shared by other factors.

[Suburbanisation] leads to urban sprawl and requires considerable land resources, which leads to the destruction of natural habitats and open spaces. (Respondent JFZ6EM3)

Distinguishing statements within **Factor 3 (Managed growth perspective)**, shared by the minority of stakeholders, present a more laissez-faire variation on Factor 1, encased in promoting urban development projects, such as new logistical centres (+3) and industrial parks (+4). Allocating land plots to such projects is prioritised over agricultural use (-3), likely dominant

in the present. A Comprehensive Plan is seen as an essential enabler of this (+4), with its organising role in steering future development highly prioritised:

[If the comprehensive plan] were to be elaborated smartly and successfully, it could become a truly strategic document for the municipality for the years to come, determining a vector for future development. (Respondent PLGU7X5)

At the same time, the proclaimed goals concerning preserving the sanitary zones around waterfront development (+3) may conflict with the general pro-growth impetus. Interestingly, this perspective strongly opposes the dedication of land for self-building for displaced households (-3). However, it is not clear what rationale is behind such a view.

Discussion

Unveiling Discrepancy Between Perspectives, Pressures, and Measures

The studied context of Ukraine reveals the possibility of a rapid and far-reaching shift of socio-political, economic, and ecological conditions directly affecting land use on the European continent. Such a possibility, driven by both external and internal pressures and factors, should be given more serious consideration in European planning research, particularly informed by the optics of preparedness, adaptiveness, and resilience (Arondi et al., 2023). The 2014-2020 governance rescaling had a major effect on the future land policy.

While the urgency of dealing with climate change, water scarcity, and the energy transition is undeniable on the (inter)national scale (Meyfroidt et al., 2022), local perspectives are fragmented regarding the priority and treatment of these issues, with some authorities questioning their relevance altogether. Q-methodology has revealed three distinct perspectives co-existing within the local authority, highlighting a concerning lack of shared positive dimensions among them. Surprisingly, the only strong consensus point across all three perspectives was to exclude regional authorities from interfering in local decision-making.

This signals a significant risk for the future of land use, as mistrust can hinder cooperation on critical common land use issues, be it river basin management, waste treatment, or nature restoration. It might also indicate a rise in localism and competition for investment, similar to what can be observed in other European contexts, from Poland, Romania (Gradinaru et al., 2023), to Italy (Mazzoleni, 2022). The lack of trust between the urban municipalities and regions is alarming, not just because it stimulates inter-municipal competition but because it effectively leaves municipalities locked within their (enlarged yet still limited) planning scale and essentially blind to larger and more pressing issues.

Such a situation of growing localism is not unique in Europe (cf Krigsholm, 2022 and Faludi, 2013) but calls for better contextualisation to be well understood. In Vinnytsia, similar to other

areas, the 2020 municipal amalgamation disregarded functional connections, instead creating an ad hoc ‘amalgam’ of the core city and hinterland territories. Challenges of a regional planning character remain quite unfamiliar to the urban municipalities, which have inherited city-centric views and thus shrug off the unknown ‘rural’ and ‘natural’ while focusing on the manageable ‘urban’.

Vinnitsia municipality has a similar composition of views as observed nationally via the Q questionnaire study, and most of the policy measures in the municipality can be directly associated with each of the perspectives. Suburban housing construction and the development of industrial areas are linked with the perspective of pro-growth promoters. The adherents of the protective perspective focus on research, mapping, and conservation of the rivers, and water management. The pragmatic perspective links the consolidation of planning control over land development via retaining municipal land ownership and developing a new Comprehensive plan. Only measures regarding the promotion of small- and medium-scale farming have not been directly related to any shared perspectives and remain somewhat unique for Vinnitsia. It also leaves room for questions about why so much agricultural land is converted into built-up land in the Comprehensive Plan.

The expected role of the Comprehensive Plan in establishing the rule-based principles of land use is reinforcing a highly territorialised view of land use pressures. Most instances of external pressures are mentally and practically cast out beyond the municipal border and disregarded. Negative externalities of such a shake-off of land use pressures are likely to be borne by the neighbouring municipality, stimulating the second authority to also disregard it within its land domain and “pass it on” further, creating a vicious circle.

Implications and Future Research Directions in Local Land Use Governance

The aim of this article was not just to uncover a ‘black box’ of local decision-making regarding land use, but to situate it in the broader theoretical context. The process of decision-making, encompassing heterogeneity of possible relationships, requires an adequate lens for analysis. We have identified that the relationship between pressures, perspectives, and measures can be understood through an institutionalist lens, providing a foundation for future research at the meso- and micro scales, as well as for comparative studies (see Figure 1). Policy measures can be seen as outcomes of the shared perspectives of key stakeholder groups within municipal administration. These perspectives are, in turn, shaped by the pressures they recognise. Pressures that are not identified by local actors, however, do not lead to policy measures, underscoring the importance of carefully calibrating researchers' biases in relation to macro-level policy expectations. Finally, the measures implemented—whether policies or direct

interventions—can be assessed for their adequacy in addressing both recognised pressures and those outside the awareness of local stakeholders.

Utilising this analytical framework in research on other territorial contexts, scales, and levels of governance would allow for building a comparative and more sophisticated understanding of the interrelation of the three components. This, in turn, would produce the vital components for learning in local land use governance, advancing much-needed policy and knowledge exchange for sustainable land use.

We claim that to be effectively implemented, macro-level policies attempting to curb the land take or to expand the size of protected natural territories must thoroughly consider the process of local land use decision-making. By directly addressing and adapting the macro-level requirements and expectations to local contexts, it might be possible to address fears, find consensus points, and build on the supportive groups within the municipality. Setting unilateral expectations will lead to misreading and misunderstanding assumptions of such policies being thrown at the municipalities, and risk major opposition to the manner and overall success of their implementation.

Conclusion

This article sought to open up the ‘black box’ of local decision-making regarding local land use in the context of Ukraine, where municipalities recently underwent the transfer of land ownership and devolution of land use and planning control. This is a crucial task as the number of land use pressures—continuing pre-war factors, war-related, and those stemming from EU regulations—is growing in number and complexity. To address this task, we devised and employed an analytical framework to explain the relationship between land use pressures and measures via the study of the stakeholders’ perspectives.

By complementing a single municipality in-depth case study with a Q-methodology study across 16 municipalities, we arrived at three major implications for policy and planning practice. First, we have identified a diversity of competing land uses challenging the notion of unidirectional urbanisation or ‘land take’, limiting the applicability of the NNLT approach. For instance, agriculture in Ukraine can be seen as a victim of urbanisation but also as an aggressor towards the green and blue areas. Its international export-oriented role makes agriculture a priority land use, and the losses of arable land in the east of Ukraine drive the need to expand and intensify soil tilting elsewhere in the country. Being constraining and insensitive to the local context, the unidimensional NNLT approach will likely face similar issues in other contexts.

Second, results also show that the newly emerging pressures are not well reflected in the views shared across municipalities. Concerns for droughts and water scarcity, soil pollution, and

placement of renewable energy or food security, not to mention expected restrictions from supranational regulations, were heavily overshadowed by more conventional pressures such as suburbanisation and industry development. Similarly, most of the local land use policies and measures come from tried and tested methods, weakly adapted to the growing complexity and scale of pressures.

Third, we have identified the limits of subsidiarity and municipal autonomy in the governance of land. The existing governance framework seems inadequate to support sustainable land use and the aims of the Nature Restoration agenda, lacking an effective mediating subnational level and coherent, locally articulated aims of national land use policy. As localism intensifies, municipal authorities remain distant and distrustful of the upper levels of governance. A pro-growth mindset among municipalities, coupled with a narrow understanding of their role and responsibility in achieving the objectives of socio-ecological transition—such as limiting soil sealing, creating new natural reserves, supporting local food networks, and preserving watershed areas—poses considerable risks of irreversible environmental transformations. Even in cases where local authorities can think beyond their immediate interest, they are trapped in the race to the bottom of inter-municipal competition for land suitable for new residential development and economic activities.

By building on these conclusions, international, national, and local policymakers can advance a more grounded approach to (supra)national land policy. At the same time, NNLT, restoration targets, and similar top-down policies need to reflect on how they can contribute to land scarcity at the local level, contrary to their implied goals. This especially concerns the territories experiencing major socio-ecological shifts, where such unilateral agendas may be met with confusion and opposition coming from missing governance arrangements, a mismatch with the local needs, or the unavailability of adequate policy instruments. The analytical approach developed in the article provides a means of assessing the local scope of measures, perceptions, and pressures and deciding on the course of policy action.

The scale of land use governance challenges for Ukrainian municipalities requires extended research in the coming years. We expect that the elaborated analytical framework will contribute to comparative studies of land use decision-making on the local level while providing the base for in-depth case studies, linking policy and land use research. Such research would strongly benefit from a more robust systematisation of land use pressures in the war context and institutional embeddedness of local land use.

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Maria Smirnova: Data Curation, Visualisation, Validation.

Conflict of interest

Maria Smirnova is a spatial planner in Vinnytsia municipality. Her work on this project was conducted in parallel with her main position, where she is involved in small river identification and the expansion of reserved areas of blue infrastructure.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Q-set and ranking by factors

Category	#	Statement	Pragmatic perspective		Protective perspective		Managed growth perspective	
			z-score	rank	z-score	rank	z-score	rank
Fiscal implications of land use	1	ATs will require more spending on infrastructure than they can bring in revenue to the local budget.	-0.38112	-1	-0.48685	-1	-0.84602	-2
	2	The land resources of AT may lead to collecting considerably more taxes in the local budget.	-0.61247	-1	-0.53674	-1	-0.22017	0
	3	To prevent the deterioration of the climate in the community, it is necessary to change the current land use.	-0.11514	0	1.0821	2	0.04873	1
Ecosystem services and Nature Fund	4	Natural areas in the municipality must be extended.	0.49551	1	1.59144	4	0.37787	1
	5	Natural environment conservation should have a priority over economic gains in the municipal land use policy.	1.05827	2	1.242	3	-0.2133	0
	6	A share of communally owned land in the municipality should remain in reserve to enable reaction to unforeseen challenges and needs in the future.	1.36731	3	0.31442	0	-0.81135	-2
	7	The development of waterfront territories and other protected areas must be severely reduced.	0.22906	0	1.26246	3	1.53242	3
Land policy	8	For the sustainable development of the community, it is better to sell, rather than lease, communal land on the AT.	-0.44853	-1	-2.22827	-4	-0.742	-1
	9	The land resources of AT help to relieve the development pressure in the administrative centre of the municipality.	-1.61083	-4	-0.85863	-2	0.78355	1
	10	It is necessary to develop and approve the Comprehensive Community Plan in order to effectively manage the land fund.	-0.00301	4	0.27797	0	2.1514	4
	11	LGs should systematically study and publish information on the state of the land fund in the community, in particular on PT.	-0.00301	0	-0.0314	0	-0.43348	0
	12	LG should limit the uncontrolled expansion of ploughed areas in the municipality.	-0.0613	0	0.01965	0	0	0
	13	LG should provide a policy that curbs the development of agricultural territories.	1.10536	3	0.43531	1	-1.16142	-3

14	Mechanisms for balancing the interests of landowners, local residents, and LG, should be elaborated within the municipality.	0.44868	1	0.91273	2	0.98279	2
15	Regional authorities should steer the land use policy concerning the AT in the municipality.	-1.51455	-3	-1.58737	-4	-1.08489	-3
16	Coordination of land use policy with neighbouring municipalities is of crucial importance.	0.43717	1	0.65666	1	0.00687	0
17	The owners of land plots must be restricted in their use rights to achieve sustainable land use.	-1.26349	-3	0.14456	0	-0.54244	-1
18	Land plots for the expansion of renewable energy generation (wind and soil) should be provided in the municipality.	-1.10182	-2	0.30192	0	-0.74887	-1
19	Logistics infrastructure is crucial for development and thus should be supported by the allocation of appropriate land plots.	0.64949	2	0.48476	1	1.40971	3
20	The expansion of ploughed areas on AT is necessary for local agricultural production.	-1.77585	-4	-0.66369	-2	-1.35379	-4
21	Industrial parks are a source of development and jobs and require more land.	1.08662	2	-0.64076	-1	1.79445	4
22	Groceries consumed by the local residents have to be predominantly grown and manufactured within the municipality.	-0.8234	-2	-0.34705	-1	0.13677	1
23	Land allocation for IDP housing is a priority task for the municipal land use policy.	-0.55129	-1	-1.04477	-2	-1.21015	-4
24	Land allocation for veterans is a priority task for the municipal land use policy.	0.42656	1	-1.20617	-3	-0.66083	-1
25	Detached and single-family housing development on AT is a priority direction for the municipality.	-0.82927	-2	-1.44902	-3	0.7976	2
26	Mixed use of land through a combination of residential, commercial and recreational functions is the key to sustainable land use.	1.62633	4	1.02829	2	1.03152	2
27	Development of neglected and abandoned areas should be prioritised over the allocation of new land plots on AT.	0.34887	0	1.32644	4	-1.02496	-2

Annex 2. List of interviewees in Vinnytsia

Interviewee	Date	No.
Senior urban planner (enterprise of Vinnytsia city council)	26/04/2024	1-M
Senior manager in economics (Vinnytsia city council)	26/04/2024	2-M
Environmental NGO representative	26/04/2024	3-C
Senior urban planner (Vinnytsia city council)	26/04/2024	4-M
Representative of the Regional Development Agency	15/05/2024	5-R
Senior manager/advisor in Agriculture (Vinnytsia city council)	07/05/2024	6-M
Local big business (investment) representative	30/04/2024	7-B
Senior project manager (enterprise of Vinnytsia city council)	16/05/2024	8-M
Senior official with political representation (Vinnytsia city council)	20/05/2024	9-M

Annex 3. Details of land use map creation (based on CORINE Urban Atlas categories)

To compare the current land use in Vinnytsia municipality with the one proposed in the Comprehensive Plan, manual spatial mapping in QGIS was applied to convert the Ukrainian classification of functional uses of territory to the standards of Urban Atlas, Copernicus Land Monitoring Service, and the European Environment Agency. The main goal was to create spatially accurate maps with classification from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service's Urban Atlas according to standards defined based on a common methodology of Eurostat and OECD for the EU member states. As these data do not yet cover Ukraine, the relevant data were manually generated based on available satellite imagery and geodata in the public domain.

In the first stage, vector data of land plots were downloaded from the Public Cadastral Map of Ukraine using a special plug-in for QGIS. Additional fields have been added to the attribute table: 'Functional purpose' and 'Designated purpose' in accordance with the Land Code of Ukraine. The available data was limited to March 2022. To remedy this, a raster file of the Zoning Plan, which was in effect before the approval of the Comprehensive Plan, was imported. It was used to fill in the gaps according to current zoning. For greater accuracy, the data was cross-checked with the satellite image from Google Maps.

In the second stage, the data was reclassified to meet the standards of the Urban Atlas. Notably, the category "Industrial, commercial, public, military, and private units" required merging several types of zoning from the Ukrainian national classifier. To facilitate the interpretation of the categories and spatial comparison, polygons from OpenStreetMap (OSM) were added to the project, which partially overlap with the categories from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. A new column was added to the cadastral layer attribute table to create a correspondence between the Ukrainian functional purpose categories and the Urban Atlas categories, where the most appropriate value from the Copernicus classification was manually assigned.

Plots with residential development and public spaces were differentiated by density: "Continuous Urban Fabric" (high-rise buildings, historic centre), "Discontinuous

Dense/Medium/Low/Very Low Urban Fabric“ - depending on the number of storeys and building type. Detached single-family housing within the city boundary was classified as “Low” density, and the one beyond as “Very Low”. The plots used for a market, hotel, or shopping mall were assigned the category “Industrial, commercial, public, military, and private units”. Schools and kindergartens up to 5 floors were classified as “Medium” density. Cultural and historical heritage sites in the inner city were classified as “Continuous Urban Fabric”. Industrial, transport, energy, and defense facilities were classified as “Industrial, commercial, public, military, and private units”. Meanwhile, airports, railways, and highways were assigned separate categories.

Agricultural land was classified mainly as Arable land. If the land was used as pasture, the category “Pastures” was assigned. Areas with small-scale farming and urban gardens were classified as “Mixed cultivation patterns”. Open spaces with sparse shrubs were classified as “Open spaces with little or no vegetation”. If the area was permanently sown with perennial crops, the “Permanent crops” category was used.

After the current land use scheme was completed, the raster layer of the Comprehensive Plan was uploaded. On its basis, a new polygon layer was manually created, where the plots were assigned categories from the Urban Atlas, similar to the previous stage. In cases where prospective development involves the completion of ongoing construction, the categories of “Continuous” or “Discontinuous Dense Urban Fabric” were assigned, depending on the density and purpose. Reserve areas for new housing construction were classified as “Construction sites”.

This approach facilitated a comparison between the current and proposed land use, and an assessment of potential transformations, preservation of functions, expansion of urbanised areas, and reduction of natural or agricultural areas.